

Reputation: Interim Report

shemakes.eu 101006203 Deliverable n. 4.2

Delivery Date: 16 December 2021

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101006203.

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Deliverable

Project acronym:	shemakes.eu
Grant agreement n.	101006203
Project title:	Opportunity ecosystems bridging the gender gap
Deliverable number	4.2
Deliverable title	Reputation: Interim Report
Version	1.0
Date	16 December 2021
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Dissemination level	PU: Public

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the reputation management Interim report, giving a general overview of the accompaniment process from M4 to M12. Reputation, in a broader sense, provides support to the shemakes.eu aims to create an inclusive, diverse, and participatory ecosystem, inspiring people to embody the shemakes vision, provide practical guidance and tools for labs and ultimately empowering future female innovators of the sustainable textile and clothing industry through inspiration, skills and networks.

This deliverable focuses on reporting the activities of the three roles Advisors, Gurus and Ambassadors and the communication strategy, giving exceptional visibility for their actions and profiles for each group, thus expanding the network and making it vibrant.

This document was directed by MATRIX as coordinator of WP4 and co-created with the direct partners, especially the task leaders (T4.1 – FLOD, T4.2 and TCBL and interviewers). Finally, in co-creative sessions with the Gurus and members of the project, particularly in the last iteration M9– M12 supporting the process of Ambassador and transfer labs in their first steps.

The **first chapter** gives an overview of the WP goals, advancements and an overview of the activities carried out by each task.

The **second, third and fourth** chapters explain the details of activities for each respective role of Advisors, Gurus and Ambassadors, accordingly their timelines, goals and giving an idea of the following steps.

The **last chapter** presents the visibility of the three groups giving an overview of the communication strategy planned, particularly their website and social media.

The document is completed with conclusions, references and annexes. Finally, the **key messages** are summarised as follows:

Through the shemakes voices and the feedback meeting, the **Advisors** left important messages on innovation, the relationship with industry, steam and media. Some of their advice:

- We have to help educators in academia to educate people towards more hybrid competency profiles.

- Extended lifecycle of T&C products: designing for a long future, not just to respond to a trend.
- It is essential to mix men and women in the shemakes.eu project. Including the men's support to change a dominant system and enabling spaces in which both can promote shemakes values, like collaboration.
- Innovation never stops! It is grounded on insights and ideas that come from the everyday curiosity for the world around us.
- Innovation comes from the confrontation of these ideas with all kinds of people, ranging from peers to quadruple-helix stakeholders (community, business, policy-makers, applied research).

The Gurus find their mission through the reflections of their activities when a strong network of knowledge transfer prepared for the next phase; some of their learnings are:

- We believe that every person can contribute something on a personal level with their motivation, commitment, competencies and skills and on a community level by sharing values and skills with a greater network.

The Ambassadors, through their applications, expressed their particular interest in being part of the shemakes network and representing the community by transmitting the values and mission in the upcoming months in the transfer labs. Here are some of their motivations:

- *I want to share this passion and experience with other women and show them that it is not the society that should shape you, but everyone should develop and expand their skills and abilities without bias.*
- *We all must take responsibility. We as a magazine that promotes fashion through our channels, feel a social and ethical responsibility in the fashion and textile industry chain. We need to write more good stories and try to fix the problems.*
- *I like being a facilitator for other people to make and achieve. I think it's often about confidence, and I enjoy guiding people in reaching this point where they're not afraid. I think shemakes is a great way to create a network of women around these topics, animate events and inspire innovation.*

The following steps will focus on integrating the message of the Advisors during the shemakes voices and the dissemination in media in the shemakes community. In the second phase, WP4 will accompany Gurus in their role, supporting transfer labs and the Ambassadors in their mission to spread the shemakes vision and adapt the content for a fruitful sharing experience from all sides.

Table of Contents

DELIVERABLE	2
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
TABLE OF CONTENTS.....	6
LIST OF TABLES	7
LIST OF FIGURES	7
1. INTRODUCTION	8
1.1 DESCRIPTION OF THE DELIVERABLE	8
1.2 CONTEXT AND OBJECTIVES	8
1.3 METHODOLOGY AND ACTIVITIES CARRIED OUT.....	9
2. ADVISORS	13
2.1 NEW ADVISORS	13
2.2 SHEMAKES VOICES.....	14
<i>The purpose.....</i>	<i>14</i>
<i>The structure.....</i>	<i>15</i>
<i>Key messages.....</i>	<i>16</i>
2.3 FEEDBACK ROUND.....	21
<i>Meeting purposes.....</i>	<i>21</i>
<i>Review of key aspects labs.....</i>	<i>22</i>
<i>Feedback/ recommendations.....</i>	<i>22</i>
2.4 NEXT STEPS.....	25
3. GURUS	25
3.1 SUPPORT DURING THE ACTIVITIES FROM WP2,3 AND 4 M4-M8	27
<i>Fab16.....</i>	<i>28</i>
3.2 ACTIVITIES SUPPORTING TRANSFER FROM PHASE 1 TO PHASE 2:	29
<i>Gift challenge.....</i>	<i>30</i>
<i>Innovation analysis.....</i>	<i>32</i>

<i>From Gurus to transfer labs:</i>	33
3.3 NEXT STEPS.....	29
4. AMBASSADORS	38
4.1 PROMOTION AND SELECTION PROCESS.....	38
4.2 APPLICATION	39
4.3 SCORING AND EVALUATION	39
4.4 OPEN DISCUSSION	41
4.5 QUANTITATIVE RESULTS	44
4.6 RESULTS	48
4.7 NEXT STEPS.....	50
5. VISIBILITY.....	51
5.1 VISIBILITY FOR ADVISORS	52
5.2 VISIBILITY FOR THE GURUS.....	53
5.3 VISIBILITY FOR AMBASSADORS.....	54
5.4 NEXT STEPS	56
6. CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK	57
7. DOCUMENT INFORMATION	58
7.1 REVISION HISTORY.....	59
7.2 STATEMENT OF ORIGINALITY	59
7.3 COPYRIGHT	59
7.4 DISCLAIMER.....	59
7.5 ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	59
8. REFERENCES	60
9. GLOSSARY	60
9.1 AGILE INNOVATION METHODS	60
10. ANNEX 1: GURUS' PROFILES.....	61
11. ANNEX 2: GURUS, TRANSFER LABS AND AMBASSADORS	65
12. ANNEX 3: SCORING AMBASSADORS	70
13. ANNEX 4: PRESENTATION INTRODUCTION REPUTATION MANAGEMENT	71

List of Tables

Table 1: Synthesis of shemakes Voices pairing shemakes partners and Advisors.	13
Table 2: List of Gurus.	22
Table 3: Innovation Analysis workshop structure.	27
Table 4: Brief timeline transfer labs Gurus and Ambassadors second phase.	28
Table 5: Scoring Ambassadors.	32
Table 6: List of Ambassadors.	39
Table 7: Paring transfer labs with Ambassadors.	40
Table 8: Communications actions for shemakes Voices.	43
Table 9: social media promotion of call for Ambassadors	46

List of Figures

Figure 1: Summary reputation management selection Advisors, Gurus & Ambassadors.	10
Figure 2: Shemakes Fabrigathering paros.	24
Figure 3: Impressions gift challenge workshop.	25
Figure 4: Ambassador applicants' experiences during the shemake activities.	34
Figure 5: Ambassador applicants. Mission-driven.	35
Figure 6: The applicants are divided into the 3 age groups.	36
Figure 7: Applicants are differentiated according to their gender.	36
Figure 8: Overview of the laboratories used by the applicants.	37
Figure 9: Overview of the applicants' activities.	37
Figure 10: Overview of the countries from which the applicants come.	38
Figure 11: Overview of the nationality of the applicants.	38
Figure 12: Overview of social media channels used by applicants.	39
Figure 13: Network visualisation on website.	45

1. Introduction

1.1. Description of the deliverable

D4.2 Reputation: Interim Report (lead partner: MATR; M12) reports on the Reputation Management activities in phase one, including the role of the Advisors, profiles of the six Gurus, identification of the 12 Ambassadors, and the pairing of Gurus and Ambassadors with the 12 'transfer' labs for the second phase.

1.2. Context and Objectives¹

As indicated in the DoA, Reputation Management focuses on promoting women innovators of excellence to help develop role models in a collective dimension. The aim is to establish communities in which different aspects of open, social and entrepreneurial innovation are promoted in multiple roles. During M4 - M12, the concept of reputation has created a space to tell stories about women as contributors and change-makers in innovation through skills, inspiration and networks. In that way, it aims to promote a positive impact on an individual level, support the shemakes community, convey examples that induce change in perceptions, and generate positive behavioural growth in both social and business contexts.

Reputation at the individual level encompasses the motivations, needs, and advice provided towards building the community of innovators. Furthermore, as shemakes promotes, reputation helps to convey strong links at a collective level, i.e. the labs, the shemakes network and, more broadly, the reputation of women in the context of T&C innovation, the ultimate goal of the project.

Reputation focuses in this deliverable particularly on developing the strategy presented in D4.1 Reputation Launch and understanding the interactions of the three roles:

¹ Description of Action of the shemakes.eu project

- **The Advisors** provide guidance to shemakes as a project and as a community with a shared goal.
- **The Gurus** are members of the shemakes partners who are the main support figures for technical and content development during the activities. They lead educational and entrepreneurial activities and will be key referents for knowledge transfer between Ambassadors and transfer labs.
- **The Ambassadors** are the spirit of the experiences lived, who will carry the shemakes flag, representing the values and skills to be transmitted to the transfer labs.

Finally, the task of **Visibility** builds a strategy to communicate all the activities of the roles described above, supported by FLOD. Centralised through the communications team, all the labs and partners play a role in accompanying this strategy through content designed to embed the new values co-created in the contexts of the shemakes labs.

1.3. Methodology and Activities Carried out

Following the delivery of D4.1, Reputation Management carried out in the next steps in parallel to accompany the three different groups on their respective timelines:

For the **Advisors' interviews**, a meeting was arranged between TCBL, FLOD and MATRIX at M6 to coordinate the shemakes Voices sessions. In this meeting, partners agreed on the objectives and a working agenda for the interviews. In total, four shemakes Voices interviews were held in the first phase.

In M11 a feedback meeting was conducted, coordinated by TCBL, MATRIX, and all the labs' participation, presenting the experiences in the first phase of activities.

The **Guru's support** process was accompanied by the planning and initiation of labs activities (M3) during bi-weekly meetings of the leaders of WP2, 3 and 4² to coordinate the specific actions of the labs. Complementary to the leaders meeting the bi-weekly meetings with the labs presented the progress and reflections of the processes through the feedback activities and preparation for following activities.

² in detail agenda of the labs meeting in the WP2,3 and 4 [Shemakes recurring lab meeting WP 2,3,4](#)

WP4 actively collaborated in presenting the reputation concept (Annex 4³) by inviting the attendees to participate in the shemakes community actively and become part of the role model community: listening to the shemakes Voices interviews, being in constant contact with the labs and Gurus, and finally participating as shemakes Ambassadors.

Finally the **Ambassadors process** started in M9. We began with the coordination and selection of the Ambassadors in close contact with TCBL, FLOD and the labs. The Ambassadors call ended in the middle of M11 and the announcement of the results in M12. This concludes the first phase of the shemakes. Thus, Reputation Management aims to ensure the successful synchronisation of the Ambassador selection and pairing with the transfer labs in the following months.

A summary of the activities can be found in figure 1.

Figure 1: Summary reputation management selection Advisors, Gurus & Ambassadors.

³ The in the following presentation content the introduction of the reputation management [Reputation Management](#)

2. Advisors

Advisors are leading figures in the areas of science, technology and industry, with an emphasis on the T&C sector, providing guidance to shemakes.eu as a project and as a community with a shared goal. In the D4.1 we introduced a group of nine prominent figures who have achieved success in a range of fields related to innovation and the textile and clothing industry. Their expertise and inspiration foster the further development of stories and examples of excellence together with the other groups of the shemakes community.

2.1. New Advisors

One of the Advisors chosen, Amber Jae Slooten, was unavailable to be involved in the project. Therefore, a new Advisor, one who could align with the concept of diversity and inclusion, was sought. In M9, Grace Jun, Director of the Open Style Lab and Professor at Parsons University in New York, joined our Advisory Board. Below is her biography:

Grace Jun⁴

CEO at Open Style Lab, Assistant Professor at the University of Georgia

Grace Jun is a professor at the University of Georgia (UGA) researching creative practices that are inclusive of disability, which manifests into outcomes such as accessible graphic design and adaptive fashion. She is also CEO of a Smithsonian National award-winning nonprofit organisation called [Open Style Lab \(OSL\)](#). Grace's commitment to designing with disability groups is reflected in her latest publication, [Universal Materiality](#), and an anticipated book on fashion & disability to be released for 2023. Grace has been featured in [Forbes](#), [New York Times Style](#), and recently the [Washington Post](#). From the White House to ABC Channel News, Grace has been asked to speak about disability and design in numerous settings around the world. She is a proud alumna of both Parsons School of Design and RISD majoring in Design & Technology (MFA) and Graphic Design (BFA) respectively. Grace has previously held positions as a UX Designer at Samsung Electronics and as an Assistant

⁴ <http://gracejun.com/>

Professor at The New School, Parsons School of Fashion. A recipient of the National Endowment for the Arts, she also serves on jury committees and organisations that advance the arts & design.

With regards to the Advisor Anna Fiscale, she has been on maternity leave since the beginning of the project and has been substituted by her equally inspiring and qualified vice, Valeria Valotto. Valotto has now confirmed that she will continue officially in this role and participate in the shemakes Voices interview as well.

Valeria Valotto

Vice-President, Quid Coop. Soc.

Valeria Valotto, born and raised in Verona, studied humanities and continued her research between England and Germany. Since 2017 she has been responsible for the impact projects office of Quid, an ethical fashion social enterprise in Verona, Italy. Quid, a young social entrepreneurship reality, was already born circular: accessories and collections are born from the recovery of textile surpluses in collaboration with Made in Italy brands, while factories and offices offer employment opportunities and professional growth to categories at greater risk of labour exclusion in Italy.

2.2. Shemakes Voices⁵

The purpose

Shemakes Voices was created to give visibility and resonance to the experience and know-how of shemakes' female Advisors. In these interviews, we share their trajectory, their successes and stories.

A set of standard questions has been developed that are modified by each interviewer after a preliminary call with and research on the Advisor. These questions aim to open a conversation on an interesting topic, for which the interviewee is passionate, in order to engage the public. The conversation is intentionally kept on a

⁵ The interview series is summarised at the following link that contains the text of the press release we created for it: <https://shemakes.eu/blog/shemakesvoices>

light and not too academic level to appeal to women of all ages, nationalities and education levels. About halfway through the interview we introduce questions about the female experience: the relevance of gender in her career and whether she experienced barriers because of it, and if she perceives the need to encourage women in her sector. These questions connect to the shemakes gender vision, but again, are part of a wider discussion that avoids dogma. We also include questions that relate specifically to her and women's contributions to a future sustainable fashion or textile industry.

The format thus poses a dialogue between the interviewer and the Advisor connected to the different themes that shemakes addresses in other WPs. This space invites us to listen, participate and reflect through personal and professional growth to a call to action towards a positive impact, which we want to address throughout the project. This format aims for a fruitful conversation that will leave a key message for the shemakes community.

The structure

The interviews match nine members of the partnership with the nine Advisors; the coordination of this matching and the preparation of interviews, dates, and their promotion is conducted in collaboration with FLOD.

The interviewers work with predefined questions and adapt them based on the advisor's topics: gender vision, lab activities, innovation, skills. Shemakes Voices runs once a month from M9 to M15. The following pairing has been proposed:

Table 1: Synthesis of shemakes Voices pairing shemakes partners and Advisors.

	Interviewer	Advisor	Topic	Timing
1	Alexandra FLOD	Becky Earley	Vision	M9 Sep
4	Kerstin Helmerdig MATRIX	Marte Henschel	Skills	M10 Oct
2	Frederique TCBL	Aurelie Mossie	Labs / innovation	M11 Nov
3	Katty TCBL	Gabriela Macoveiu	Policy / innovation system	M12 Dec
5	Kerstin Junge TIG	Valeria Valotto	Vision	M13 Jan
6	Adriana MATRIX	Mara Balestrini	Labs(maker)	M14 Feb
7	Giovanni Giusti FLOD	Daniela Toccafondi	Policy / innovation	M15 Mar
8	Anastasia IAAC	Grace Jun	Skills	M15 Mar
9	Cecilia WAAG	Silvia Brandi (atlas of the future)	Vision	M17 May

Key messages

Becky Earley⁶

Becky Earley is a design researcher and co-director of Centre for Circular Design (CCD). Her practice research encompasses making materials and prototypes, exhibition curation and writing. She is also a highly skilled workshop facilitator and communicator, specialising in the translation of cross disciplinary design-led research into commercial contexts for sustainable fashion textiles and other fields.

Earley kicked-off the shemakes Voices series with an inspiring interview about her diverse background, her researching activities and her future plans.

- **Background:** The first part of the interview was focused on Earley's diverse background. She described her years as a student at Central Saint Martins in

⁶ See the written interview with video at <https://shemakes.eu/shemakes-voices-becky-earley>

London and her feeling of being at “the heart of fashion” underlining the importance of having formal studies, learning the core skills that can provide the necessary tools and frameworks to then go off and innovate. She also outlined her first research activity on “exhausted print” that led to her work being exhibited at the Victoria & Albert Museum in London as a prototype of sustainable innovation in T&C design.

- **T&C industry:** In the second half of the interview Earley made an analysis and logical reasoning of the current situation of the T&C industry. She underlined the importance of innovating and always offering something different than what can be found on the market. She stressed the importance of taking risks, following your own instincts while having a clear, structured idea of what you want to do in the medium and long term. She explained that there is no reason to be afraid of asking for help: mentoring is fundamental for those who are looking for the right direction.
- **Future plans:** The third and final part of the interview focused on what the T&C industry can do to combat climate change and improve environmental performance. This statement that Earley used at the end probably sums up her outlook on life, work and the industry: *“If you’re involved in sustainability, you just really want things to change and you work really hard.”*

Key ideas of the interview:

- Innovation starts from formal studies: know the fundamentals before starting to innovate.
- Feedback is important: don’t be afraid to ask. If it’s not what you were expecting, start again.
- Each product has its own story: uniqueness is the key, mass production isn’t.
- Extended lifecycle of T&C products: designing for a long future, not just to respond to a trend.

Marte Hentschel⁷

Marte Hentschel’s background is very diverse: having started off as a men’s tailor, she has experience in fashion and apparel design. She is one of the most important entrepreneurs in the textile industry in Germany and is now CEO at [Sgetch](https://sgetch.com), a software provider and innovation agency that helps search, connect and manage T&C production all in one place.

⁷ See the written interview with video at <https://shemakes.eu/shemakes-voices-hentschel-marte>

After an initial discussion with Marte, the guiding questions were formulated. Primarily addressed individual aspects that had been filtered out in the initial interview.

- What is the absolute coolest thing you've had the chance to work on?
- Tell us more about your current business. Was there a turning point that made you realise the need to personally do something to make changes in the textile and fashion industry?
- From our STEM-Projects for young people we have learned how important volunteering is: for the projects but also for the volunteers themselves. What are your experiences in this field?
- How important are for example skills in the technological sector, in engineering? And what about social skills and talent?
- Do you think there is a need to encourage women to work in your sector? And how might we do that together?
- What advice do you have for women innovators?

Key ideas of the interview:

- Marte speaks very inspiringly about her resumé: From her perspective, it is helpful to have different experiences to be successful in the T&C industry.
- Diversity is always beneficial. Diverse teams are more successful, more productive, supportive and there's less fluctuation.
- The T&C sector is very stereotypic: the more down you go in the supply chain, the more women work in these fields. When she is teaching design classes, usually nine out of ten of her students are women, but when it comes to technology conferences, she often finds herself being the only woman.
- There is a misconception about how people consider STEM subjects and design aesthetics and soft skills. They're not different and they actually work together. Three solutions proposed:
 - We need to bring engineering coding and development into design, management and leadership education.
 - We also have to train engineers to think like a designer, like a creator.
 - We have to help educators in the academies to educate people towards more hybrid competency profiles.

Learnings:

Her advice for young women:

- Don't start alone. Team up with people who are supportive and have complimentary skills that may help you to learn and evolve.
- Don't be afraid to ask. People are surprisingly supportive when you ask, very frankly, for help.
- Let's network!

Aurélie Mossé⁸

In the interview, we focussed on three topics: Aurélie's career path, gender issues and innovation issues.

Aurélie's key ideas on these subjects were:

- **Career path:** She always wanted to be a (fashion) designer, from a very early age. The support of her mother as well as the encouragement from Christian Lacroix and fibre artists, were key in sustaining her confidence in choosing this path. She was always concerned with tactility, tangible artefacts as well as multiculturalism. So she decided to learn solid basics in textile, before moving higher on the practice-led research path, in design schools with specific programs on sustainability, creativity and interdisciplinarity. That led her to Denmark, UK and back to France, where she co-founded the Soft Matters research group at Ecole des Arts Déco. There she is now developing a research project at the crossroads between architecture, microbiology and design, the first of its kind for a young researcher project (JCJC) financed by the National Agency for Research in France.
- **Gender issues:** For her, the reality is that there are more women than men among post-graduate textile design students, as textile or clothing have long been associated with "feminine" stereotypes. However, she believes that both collectively and individually, we should aim at accepting our "masculine" as well as our "feminine" side. Researchers are human beings and should use both their rational ("masculine") and emotional ("feminine") cognitive systems. Convergence and a more fluid approach in both areas, would help to explore questions and solutions with greater depth as well as creativity.
- **Innovation issues:** She believes that innovation has to be merged with sustainability and can be inspired from nature itself. We have known for a long time (since the 1970s) that the consumption of resources on our planet should not exceed those available, but naturally, this agenda is coming back with quite some strength, even if the last Conference of the Parties (COP26)

⁸ See interview and video at <https://shemakes.eu/shemakes-voices-aurelie-mosse>

was not a great success. She believes that biomimetics and especially bio-design are key methodologies for innovation, as living organisms have smart ways of producing things with little impact on the environment (an example of this could be creating a chair directly from growing wood or growing bacteria to produce pigments).

What does it mean for shemakes?

- It is essential to explore all talents and potentials that women have in themselves, recognise them and help them use this potential in their career path.
- It is important to mix men and women in the shemakes.eu project. However, it is also important to distinguish what kind of activities are appropriate in mixed groups and under which conditions (e.g. relative maturity, status etc. of girls and women involved).
- Innovation never stops! It is grounded on insights and ideas that come from the everyday curiosity for the world around us. It also comes from confronting these ideas with all kinds of people, ranging from peers to quadruple-helix stakeholders (community, business, policy-makers, applied research).
- For such confrontation, innovation should be made tangible through prototypes or minimum viable solutions.

Gabriela Macoveiu

The interview, recorded in Romanian and published with subtitles, focuses on the career of Ms. Macoveiu, from a technical position to one that concerns regional and EU development. The discussion focused on her personal life as well as her opinions on the T&C industry and how to make it attractive to future generations and to move it towards a sustainable path.

- **Career path:** We begin with Ms. Macoveiu's change of career 22 years ago from an established position as Technical Chemical Engineer, leading a 450-person team in the textile synthetic fibres industry, to regional development. She is very proud of her current work, which involves a team of 31 experts and inspires and brings value to the region and at the EU level in 3 different fields: innovation, external cooperation and organisational communication.
- **Innovation issues:** Since 2008, Ms. Macoveiu has been coordinating the North East Region's Smart Specialization Strategy⁹ including the "entrepreneurial discovery" process that engages with local stakeholders. Her involvement in regional policy is tied to the selection of the Textile & Clothing sector as one of

⁹ See <https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>

the regional priorities. This is because of the historical role of the lasi garment production district, with a critical mass of companies as well as the oldest Technical University with its T&C Department. Her position, as facilitator of a constructive dialog between the quadruple helix representatives, allows her to provide support in finding the most viable value creation strategies and the financial and other resources needed for incremental and sustainable implementation.

- She also speaks about the Cradle to Cradle Network, where she developed a strategic plan focused on respect for the next generations through acknowledgement, assessment and actions to carry out the needed changes in order to reduce, reuse and consider waste as a new resource following the cradle to cradle concept.
- **Gender issues:** Another theme discussed was the importance of knowledge acquisition and continuous upgrading and updating of skills and competences based on strong human values. This led to speaking about the position of women in this field in an Eastern European country, where proving one's self is a challenge that requires hard work, honest self-evaluation, strong mind-setting and resilience. She highlighted the importance of leading by example and keeping one's promises. Her advice to future female entrepreneurs is to find ways to overcome the challenges of being a woman in innovation, because the long term benefit for everyone makes it truly worthwhile. Her motto is "discover, develop, act."

2.3. Feedback round

The second meeting of the Advisory Board was scheduled on November 19th, 2021 from 10.00 to 12.00 and was attended, beyond the shemakes project participants, by Silvia Brandi, Aurélie Mossé, Daniela Toccafondi, and Gabriela Macoveiu. Rebecca Earley added her insights in a separate call on November 26th and the other Advisory Board members were invited to view and comment on the presentations and draft report online.

Meeting purposes

The purpose of this meeting was to first present the results of the first phase of activity and specifically the outcomes of the three Learning Paths of WP2 and the three Innovation Services of WP3. From there, the aim was to gain feedback from the

Advisory Board members on the result achieved, the issues raised, and the strategic directions for the future.

Review of key aspects labs

Following a brief introduction, the Gurus representing each of the 6 shemakes labs briefly presented the work carried out in the first phase of activity, focusing on specific results:

- Nuria Robles of FabLab Leon presented the Curiosity Path (girls aged 8-18), with two core results: an “e-monster” doll integrating electric circuitry and a “mini-fabricademy”.
- Christina Olivotto of Onl’Fait presented the Discovery Path (young women aged 18-25) showed the results of interaction with the HEAD fashion school and a bootcamp with fashion students on leather molding, modular, fashion and e-textiles.
- Cecilia Raspanti of Waag presented the Innovation Path, with career mapping and job positioning analysis through questionnaires and interviews with Fabricademy graduates.
- Andreea Sofronea of REDU presented work on Community Engagement, exploring the gender gap and inclusive entrepreneurship through interviews, a questionnaire, a workshop and a bootcamp.
- Anastasia Pistofidou and Marion Real of IAAC presented the first Lab-to-Lab Project on wool: exploring the value chain and launching research groups on local ecosystem mapping, natural dyeing, and (DIY) tool making.
- Eléonore Huon-Merceur and Victor Senave from makesense presented the work on Business Engagement, with labs researching their local contexts, a workshop on solving challenges and an exchange with local women entrepreneurs.

The presentation including both the introduction and the lab activities is available at [this link](#).

Feedback/ recommendations

This presentation was followed by a discussion among the Advisory Board members present, first highlighting the positive results and then identifying four issues: the role of men, links with industry, links with policy, and the role of the media.

General impressions on the lab activities

Work done was noted for the scope of the work, the range of topics covered, the range of age groups, and above all the coherent vision that emerges from the integration of all these elements. The members present were impressed with the actions and the singular as well as the collective approach. A key strength is the link to entrepreneurship and long-term education, as well as the potential impact this project can have on both the TCBL and Fabricademy networks.

The role of men

Curiosity about the role of men. If the aim is to bridge the gender gap, what is the role of men in the project? Isn't it about re-balancing the roles of men and women? The project shows efficient actions, but the question is how we make them last in the long-term (after the project). For this, we need to engage men and we need to have an impact on different social backgrounds (and not only in higher education).

On the other hand, we also need to maintain a safe space for women to experiment together and develop confidence. In fact, men generally don't realise they are imposing their agenda and methods so women don't feel entitled to express themselves.

So, while we should not change the basic lab format, we need to find ways to invite men to take different roles and to establish dialogues and ways to collaborate, through caring and inspiration. The idea is to allow an exchange in which: men can explore their sensitivity and their fragility, in specific spaces and occasions. Both women and men can change a dominant system and mainly focus on men in their role of supporting and enabling women to change perspectives. These actions provide the ultimate goal to focus on the shemakes values and mission, promoting collaboration.

The project produces guidelines and approaches, very spontaneously, because we are women, and we should continue studying the men's issue: how they think; how they reflect; how they can put themselves in women's shoes.

Links with industry

Industry has a huge sustainability problem that women can positively impact. This encourages us to explain why the industry needs women to lead this change. Almost all of us have been working in sustainability beyond business as usual.

It is important to reflect on tomorrow's activities and develop even more activities with the help of a community of experts. Each shemakes lab should have a community of practitioners and mentors, belonging to the two worlds of business

and university; sustainability is the overarching issue, although this can be specified depending on the areas each lab is working on. University and the fashion industry are natural partners: prototyping, testing etc. and of course we should try to address the industry's needs.

This link between industry and university should take the advantage of the existence of the community of practice around each TCBL laboratory and try to fertilise this dialogue in a similar manner with the community of mentors activated around a business incubator. Shemakes could include these experts in round table discussions at national and international level that are more business oriented and drive innovation and business model transformation, e.g.: The round table model allows people to understand each other (engineer with commerce, textile designer with fashion designer etc.). Perhaps choose a subject and have regular round tables for that topic.

Another approach could include e.g. the organisation of an Ideathon with an international community of mentors. It is good to meet and exchange inspiring ideas, but it is also good to meet to find solutions and partners for specific problems. This would build very specific partnerships with a cluster or a group of companies that are already very engaged. This would require selecting a limited number of topics from the broad range of shemakes activities to focus on in order to facilitate business interaction. So it is not only about discussion, but about working together and creating some concrete activities together.

The questions are: what do we want to make with the industry? Why do we want to engage with them? Valorise the (women's) skills? Deal with issues? Bring new perspectives? They always indicate that they want to bring extra innovative talents, but they have limited resources and time to attend meetings.

Links with policy

When businesses meet the region, the question is how to encourage people to understand and use policy instruments. In 2 out of 3 regions, SMEs are not interested, because they do not have time to build the administrative tools to comply with EU bureaucracy. On the other hand, the Smart Specialisation model has created a platform that offers new innovation perspectives and improves integration into the regional business ecosystems.

Policy is important even for a microenterprise. Businesses must understand that loud voices are heard only when a critical mass is speaking. So in short, participating in public consultation/dialogue meetings with various departments and programs is time well spent when there is a well-defined gap in resources for investment. The shemakes project should reflect on how partners can support this approach. Is it

enough to present the project results to interested parties? We should ensure that each lab is actively involved in such dialogues – maybe a project meeting could explore this issue and find out what has already been done and can be recommended to the others as good practice.

Finally, the work in shemakes shows how interconnected issues are in policy – digital innovation, industrial transformation, circular economy, gender equality are all issues addressed by policy silos. When you have such a holistic perspective, it is difficult to engage different departments and programmes and make them see the connections.

The role of the media

The role of media – not so much social media, but rather the ‘official’ media in the industry – is often underestimated, especially when it comes to shaping perceptions related to issues such as the role of women. We need to involve the media to change the conversation – the media have the power to change the conversation on women and on sustainability.

2.4. Next Steps

The next steps for the Advisory Board include first, a continuation of the shemakes Voices series as scheduled. In addition, a second feedback meeting is scheduled for July 2022, to provide insights on the work carried out in the second phase of activities throughout the extended network of 18 labs.

Finally, Advisory Board members will be invited to participate in the final conference, scheduled in conjunction with the next edition of TCBL Days for November–December 2022. The specific forms of engagement – keynotes, round table, etc. – will be defined as part of the planning of the overall conference.

3. Gurus

The Gurus are staff members of the project partners who lead educational and entrepreneurship activities within the partners’ labs, thus activating their local communities. They show practical steps towards gender equality as community

leaders. Moreover, they represent the valuable support and charisma of the shemakes network of women role models.

As the DoA mentions, the Gurus contribute with:

- *Capture relevant knowledge from on-going research and/or activities within the Fabricademy and TCBL networks and be able to contextualise it in specific lab settings.*
- *Project knowledge and innovation developed in specific lab communities through the shemakes.eu network.*
- *Accompany the integration of new labs into the network that are interested in their specific line of activity.*

Selection and changes

The Gurus were selected from the women entrepreneurs of the lab's partners, through the Fabricademy and TCBL network. Gurus are mostly women who have been working on a long trajectory in digital manufacturing, education and entrepreneurship in the textile sector of the fashion industry.

- They have a high level of expertise due to their skills, experience and initiatives.
- They have been recognised and identified as leaders in their labs and communities.
- They will help foster exchange between the local and global community mentoring through their expertise and best practises of Learning Paths and Innovation Services.

As already stated in D4.1, six Gurus were nominated. In addition, we have two new Gurus: Cecilia Raspanti, founder of Fabricademy and representative of WAAG and Victor Senaver, who represent MAKE and brings the skills of entrepreneurship and agile innovation to the project. In the table below you can find the final group of eight Gurus that will accompany the process of the second phase of shemakes.

Table 2: List of Gurus.

Name	Field	Expertise	Organisation	Country
Anastasia Pistofidou	Architecture	Co-Founder FabTextiles lab / Co-Founder Fabricademy	IAAC	ES
Nuria Robles	Mechanical Engineering	FabLab Manager STEM education	LEON	ES
Cristina Olivotto	Physics Science Education and Communication	FabLab Manager	ONLF	CH
Cecilia Raspanti	Fashion Design	Co-Founder TextileLab Amsterdam/ Co-Founder Fabricademy	WAAG	NL
Beatriz Sandini	Business Administration	Fashion Business management Brand of sustainable fashion Cor-Botanicals	WAAG	NL
Andrea Sofronea	Performing & Theoretical Arts Fashion	Zero Waste shop Project support at Mai bine NGO	REDU	RO
Victor Senave	Entrepreneur	Trainings for young entrepreneurs	MAKE	FR

In the Annex 1. We will provide a more detailed profile of each shemakes Guru member.

3.1. Support during the activities from WP2, 3 & 4 M4-M8

During the months of April and May, Reputation Management collaborated with WP learning path and innovation services in the construction of the activities. The Gurus

worked actively during bi-weekly meetings¹⁰, in which WP leaders and the Gurus made a schedule for the conception, planning and documentation of the activities. Throughout these months, all Gurus took an active part in producing activity templates (in more detail, see D2.2) and in the construction of working guides and documentation of their activities compiled in the Open Toolkit repository (in more detail, see D3.2).

We created a general presentation (annex 3¹¹) to introduce the concept of WP4 in the different activities and support the Gurus in their mission to accompany the reputation presence and especially to explain the idea of the three proposed roles. Especially here, the Gurus of the respective labs could be identified as characters who offer support during the activities and stay in direct contact. Finally, we invite the shemakes attendees to be part of the community, to apply as shemakes Ambassadors, or join our community by staying tuned via our website and especially to have close contact with the local lab and Gurus. Some of the activities that we supported in the WP4 are: the presentation of the concept of ambassadors during the sessions of the WP2 learning paths, like the KICK-Off Innovation path, and events such as 3rd International FabWomen Conference during the international women's day, or the start-up week within other activities developed by WP2 and WP3.

Fab16

One of the significant activities we collaborated on with WP2 and WP3 was the Fab16 international conference, which gathered several Gurus physically and virtually, where different activities were carried out for the local and global resonance of the event. The following is an abstract of the activity documented by the learning path¹².

Between 08-15 of August, IAAC, MATRIX, WAAG, ONLF, LEON coordinated a "Fabrigathering community event" consisting of a peer-to-peer learning week with a series of workshops open to local and global communities, facilitated by the lab

¹⁰ The recurring bi-weekly meetings report could be found in more detail in the following link:

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1TVZ69XeZWZ5aCdRspkpwMkqmWksjxQdSIIGB92JisTY/edit?usp=sharing>

¹¹ The in the following presentation content the introduction of the reputation management and their three roles particularly the Ambassadors [Reputation Managment](#)

¹² Extract mentioned in the D2.2 Discovery week with Fabricademy and Fab Lab community- 8-13 August 2021

Gurus and the broader Fabricademy and FabLab ecosystem. While the experience fostered internal research within shemakes labs both in community engagement activities and Lab to Lab research actions around wool dyeing and tool making; Rewool workshops, Gender vision workshop by WAAG, (in WP3), it has also created an original Discovery learning path (WP2) for external participants of the Fab16 conference. Participants could choose which module they would like to attend and participate without any charge. During the week, participants could attend up to different workshops among "From Soft robotics to biobotics", facilitated by Matrix and IAAC, "Leather moulding and Grasshopper" by ONLF, [Modular garments](#) and [E-monsters](#) by LEON,

Figure 2: Shemakes Fabrigathering paros.

Lessons learned in this activity:

This gathering reminds us of the value of meeting physically as humans, as a living community and the power of understanding that **the ultimate goal of a true network is to support each other**, to bring skills together and to reflect on how to migrate from fields of research to expanding our community. This conference gave us the chance to learn from each other and continue on to the next chapter of shemakes, always growing together¹³.

3.2. Activities supporting transfer from Phase 1 to Phase 2:

As mentioned in D4.1, we proposed some activities to support the Guru's role :

- The Growth Challenge, now called **Gift Challenge**, involved the Guru's contribution for the next phase.

¹³ <https://shemakes.eu/blog/fab16-reflections> conclusions Fab 16 reflections

- The **Innovation Analysis** was planned and postponed to the next year and will be carried out in digital format.
- Finally the activity "**From Gurus to transfer labs**" aimed to bring the Gurus and Ambassadors together with the 12 'transfer' labs. It is now seen more as a larger process of constant support to the labs during M3 to M11. This was concretised mainly at the consortium meeting in Barcelona with the practical application of the shemakes innovation ecosystem canvas for the Gurus and members of the shemakes community, which will be applied in the second phase.

Gift challenge¹⁴

This workshop has been conceived to support knowledge transfer and to identify the key and contribution (the gift) that consortium members and particularly Gurus can give to the next phase of the project.

We believe that each of the shemakes roles can contribute in a particular form: on a personal level with their motivation, commitment, competencies and skills; on a community level by sharing values that strengthen the shemakes network. Thus, we aim to promote the growth of leaders who guide with confidence, respect, and courage, which are the values we hope will support the community's development with positive changes. Ultimately this dynamic is created to strengthen the network and understand how we can collaborate and support each other with the analogy of fibres and textiles that weave stronger fabrics "shemakes weave".

¹⁴ Details of the Gift challenge can be also found in the following link:
<https://shemakes.eu/blog/intangible-gift-exchange>

Figure 3: Impressions gift challenge workshop.

In this challenge, we explored with the shemakes members three essential points:

- **Their Story:** Sharing their stories of what inspired them to become a Guru, what marked their lives and defined their career paths; with the goal of connecting and empathising with the three types of audience: children, youngs and adults.
- **The Gift:** A unique contribution that the Gurus provide to the project and beyond that to the world, which can be represented in an artefact or in their knowledge that they want to pass on from one generation to another (Tell us what you are most excited about).
- **The Colour:** Their mood and the way the person imprints daily life. It also represents their personality. In other words, with this part we want to understand how emotions can create synergies in a group.

Lessons learned :

Through sharing in a physical and a safe space, each participant told their own story about their experiences and presented tangible artefacts, with contributions through teaching, passion for technology, science and exploration of new challenges.

In an open discussion each member offered a “gift” motivating all types of audience and transmitting their passion to the project with some of the stories:

- "everyone is the protagonist of their own story"
- "making the complex easy"
- "transforming manual arts into technology for learning"
- "trying to get the best out of people"
- "transforming the passion for science into novel sustainable textile research"

Further reflections are compiled in the this mural¹⁵.

Ideally, the activity is carried out with the Ambassadors to understand their mission-driven pursuit, to contribute and expand the network the “*shemakes weaving*”. Thus, Ambassadors can first recognise each Guru's support role in carrying out the activities in the transfer labs. Additionally, they can help each other and share their experiences, stories and skills as “gifts” for our shemakes community.

Innovation Analysis

The purpose of the activity, already explained in the last deliverable, is to provide a common understanding of innovation and innovation skills to identify skill gaps related both to individuals and labs.

During this workshop, Gurus will share their practises and knowledge by using and recognizing agile innovation methods in the lab context. The results could be complemented and generate new reflections for all labs and foster the application of agile innovation tools to improve the workflows in the community.

Participants: 8 Gurus

Duration: 60-120 min

Date: TBD

Structure: The following table 3 can be found in the workshop structure.

¹⁵ Mural link gift Challenge:

<https://app.mural.co/t/matrixgmbhcokg0728/m/matrixgmbhcokg0728/1638954211924/e291198cd45cafb74c7cc48ba85ddb1928320fde?sender=conferencing10443>

Table 3: Innovation Analysis workshop structure.

What	Time	Exercise and questions
Group discussion	20-30 min	Co-creation board digital What does innovation mean to you? How do you define innovation?
Process, methods and instruments in innovation	30-45 min	Introduction of different instruments and methods of agile innovation e.g: Design Thinking, Design Sprint, Scrum. This task will be moderated in the co-creation board. When developing products/implementing ideas: Is there a recurring process that you follow? (Describe this...) Which instruments and methods do you use when developing products / implementing ideas? (Which ones do you know, which ones do you use, which ones are taught in the lab practises?)
Knowledge gap	15-30 min	What areas/methods would interest you most? Where do you need to learn more? Which topics would be particularly relevant in FabLabs? Where do you see a knowledge gap?

In the following link you can find the co-creation activity that will take place during the workshop: For the transfer labs, the same activity could be applied and the same analysis performed.

From Gurus to transfer labs:

As previously announced, the Gurus to transfer activity was carried out as an accompanying process during the months from M1 to M12. In the following part, we focus on an overview of the final development of the first phase, especially on the adaptation of the innovation methodology to phase two of the project.

Process

Gurus had an intensive period of innovation actions in the phase 1 (months 4 to 9), including the first iteration of the shemakes.eu labs activities - learning paths and

innovation services. From September, labs and WP2,3,4 developed different reflection, documentation, and feedback stages. Gurus are in process of documenting the activities of WP2 and WP3 in the Open Toolkit.

Completing the practical part, after M9, the shemakes vision finalised their efforts delivering a fundamental part of the conceptualisation of the whole project. We aimed to adapt the conceptual approach provided by the gender vision as an essential part of the implementation of shemakes.

During the consortium meeting in Barcelona (M12) Gurus and SU partners worked together to develop the step-by-step operationalisation of the shemakes ecosystem canvas. This workshop creates a systematic timeline of activities for the Gurus, transfer labs and Ambassadors. Particularly in the reputation management area, this timeline supports the innovation processes with each of the shemakes actors, makes the processes accessible, and accompanies the development of the second phase from January to June, aiming to:

- Empower and highlight the importance of the contribution of each member of shemakes among the Gurus, Ambassadors and staff of the transfer labs.
- Stimulate multifaceted innovation (social, technical, organisational and institutional) and thus increase competencies.
- Makes a positive impact on the different local and global actors.
- Connect our local “shemakes” labs efficiently with a very clear process.
- Generate creative outcomes from knowledge and diversity.

The timeline structure

This timeline was intended to create a structure of one or two **recurring meetings per month**. The groups reviewed and planned a first draft with the inputs and goals for each side of the shemakes, the transfer lab and the Gurus.

At the beginning of each meeting, it was proposed to present **an introduction by the Gurus and SU members** to reflect a constructive and exemplary process. Thus the Gurus can support and help the transfer labs and Ambassadors in the course of the meetings.

Table 4 provides an overview of the timeline for **pairing** partner labs and transfer labs as a guide to be developed in close collaboration with the WPI, 2,3 and 4 packages. An extended table with a first draft of the timeline and the respectable information for Gurus, the transfer labs and Ambassadors can be found in annex 2.

Table 4: Brief timeline transfer labs, Gurus and Ambassadors second phase.

Meeting	Action	Input	Month
	Introduction of shemakes: 1 Background - Evaluation (session for all)	<i>SU members and especially Gurus will introduce the project, the objectives shemakes vision and modus operandi.</i>	M13
	Exploration: local ecosystem and motivation in their shemakes activities (split section) 2	<i>Map of the Activities, key partners and role models, how the partner labs develop their activities.</i>	M14
		Input from the Gurus, contributions and motivations.	
	Preparation: of the activity session for all and co-creation divided per task 3	Tools, methods, skills. Mapping elaborated by the transfer labs (special input by mini-workshops).	M14
		Activity canvas	
		Review preparation	

4	Making "the activity" (<i>split activity divided per task and schedule</i>)	Open Toolkit guidelines for activities.	M15 – M16
5	Transfer (<i>split section</i>)	Documentation and deliverable. e.g documentation Open Toolkit.	M17
6	Next steps <i>Preparation call new action (session for all)</i>	Guidelines promotion Ambassadors and local shemakes lab ecosystem engagement.	M18

Open Discussion

During an hour and a half session, Gurus and SU members met in groups and shared different perspectives on the development and accompaniment of transfer labs. After the division into four groups, the members shared their results and reflections for the transfer labs and the Ambassadors. Finally, the project coordination groups highlighted the importance of presenting the different project frameworks, innovation and creative input, and introducing a technical framework.

They also discussed the idea of sharing and what is required in clear terms for the labs and the Ambassadors: what shemakes will contribute as a project (giving) and what shemakes will receive in return, i.e. their commitment and duties during the development of their tasks.

The Gurus from Make and Leon also mentioned the importance of personalised support, especially for the Ambassadors, to build skills in public speaking and confidence in the realisation and preparation of the workshops.

The session ended with some ideas on how to motivate and invite labs and Ambassadors to continue participating in the shemakes community.

3.3. Next steps

Gurus will be a crucial contact point for the Ambassadors and transfer labs, bringing charisma, values, and practical support in the second phase.

We described in the last phase some activities that will be adapted in close collaboration between the Gurus and SU members to fulfil the optimal support for the next phase with the following essential points:

- Gurus will support in the onboarding process and helping the transfer labs to understand their local ecosystem, as was done in the first phase. They will support the Ambassadors in individual ways depending on the group e.g. through curiosity tasks, providing tools and special training for the girls to exercise their public speaking skills.
- The Gurus will support each task individually to adapt the activity to the requirements and its promotion.
- Gurus will be in contact with their transfer labs and Ambassadors to support all coordination of the individual process during this period.
- Gurus will communicate and support the documentation process in the Open Toolkit as well as in the formal part delivered for the project.
- Encourage the Ambassadors and transfer labs to involve the new shemakes leaders in the further exchange and active community engagement.

4. Ambassadors

4.1. Promotion and selection process

Ambassadors are girls, young women and women innovators who have participated in shemakes.eu activities in WPs 2 and 3, and demonstrate the capacity to emerge as leaders and 'carry the message' to their peers in other cultural and geographical contexts, thus acting as a multiplier mechanism for the shemakes.eu network.

During M9 and M12, the following activities were carried out: the call for Ambassadors, the evaluation, selection, and the communication of the results.

During the call, the communication team published various posts on social media and on the website. Furthermore, each lab shared the call via email to reach as many potential Ambassadors as possible.

In the online application, we have provided information on all the possible areas of interest for the Ambassadors such as:

- Benefits of being an Ambassador
- Characteristics of a great Ambassador
- Task as shemakes Ambassador
 - Support the transfer labs
 - Develop and replicate
 - Promote and share
 - Document and report
- Eligibility criteria
- Timeline
- Contact
- Link for application form

We also provided a downloads section with two items: the PDF application form served as a guide for the application process and the data consent for the parent's signature in case of minors.

At the following link, you can find the information published on the website <https://shemakes.eu/ambassadors-call> in detail.

4.2. Application

The list of questions was developed in collaboration with the labs, TCBL and FLOD, making the content and language accessible to the different target groups. Our aim was to create a questionnaire with few questions to make the process simple for everyone, while considering their experience in the activities they previously attended, as well as their interest and engagement as a future Ambassador.

The application form summarises the following questions:

- Name of the activity? (Which activity was done in the past?)
- Have you had a chance to work with or meet a shemakes "Guru" listed below?

Activity and contact to a Guru/community:

- (With which FabLabs or Gurus had the attendee worked the person in the past?)

Shemakes activities learning:

- What did you learn in these activities, and why do you think it was important to your growth as a person?

Mission driven:

- Why do you think you would be a good shemakes Ambassador? (Indicate why you want to be an Ambassador, what you can offer to others, but also what you can gain or how this opportunity will help you in any way.)

Relevant experience:

- Have you participated in any relevant laboratories or workshops, or do you have any specific training that might be relevant to your role as an Ambassador?

Training experience:

- Do you have any experience teaching anything or explaining things to a group?

4.3. Scoring and evaluation

The evaluation process was done primarily in contact with the labs. MATRIX shared an excel sheet with the following parameters mentioned in table 5. Examples were named to understand a comparative evaluation, and Gurus collaborated in adapting these criteria. In the Annex 3 you can find the final scoring list.

Table 5: Scoring Ambassadors.

Specification	Scoring
Activity and contact to a Guru/community	15%
Shemakes activities learnings	30%
Mission Driven	35%
Labs experience	10%
Teaching experience	5%
General questions	5%
TOTAL	100%

Each lab evaluated their applicants involved in the local labs. Additionally, a second lab carried out a pairing review to guarantee a fair assessment for all applicants during one week.

Pairing labs:

- Waag - laac
- On l' Fait - Leon
- Redu - Make

The 24th of November, Gurus and labs met to discuss both scores. In total 6 labs and 10 Evaluators reviewed all applications. On this day, all labs were meant to internally discuss their results to compare local experiences and share them in the group.

4.4. Open discussion

The Gurus argued mainly to value local participation in the activity, to identify and follow the contact to the original Guru. Additionally, Gurus seek a diverse group and even provide opportunities for different participants from all kinds of hybrid, online and local activities.

Another point that the labs and Gurus highlighted was whether the Ambassadors feel capable to teach and spread the message of shemakes in another country, representing the vision and methodologies that shemakes pursue.

Finally, the decisive point was their motivation to be an Ambassador and the experience and expertise they gained during the workshops and in contact with the labs. The main objective of the Ambassadors is to bring the spirit of shemakes activities and represent a group of future women innovators. We want to share some of the impressions based on two questions:

- What did you learn in these activities, and why do you think it was important to your growth as a person?
- Why do you think you would be a good shemakes Ambassador?

In the following Figure you can find an overview of their answers.

How to make bioplastic with Kombucha, how to tint tissues with bacteria in "symbiosis" with the environment; nature is amazing by all the presents she gives us! The importance to transmit those great experiments and precious knowledge about our Nature!

I became conscious of everything I still don't know, the knowledge needed to work with sustainable material alternatives. Becoming aware of these new materials, completely changed my perception and value of what is considered "a good design" in different creative design fields.

Networking with these people brought me a sense of purpose and a broader understanding of the importance of education and possibilities for women in the space.

It's great to meet a group of empowering females working within the fab lab community. It gives me extra motivation to continue the work I've been doing in coaching in a fab lab setting for all minority groups.

Studying Fashion, I learned about materials and experimented with digital design. Taking the less "traditional" designer career path, I dived into bridging craftsmanship and makerspaces to interactive user experiences. My goal is to apply what I have learned from other cultures and different learning methodologies to focus on social innovation that connects design creativity to S.T.E.M. practices that are accessible to younger audiences.

The enormous potential that lies in the encounter between women, in sharing our knowledge and organizing ourselves to build a presence in a world where positions of power and access to knowledge and technology are often denied to us. I learned that there are many of us who have similar interests and a great desire to build new approaches to knowledge and work together, and that sharing among people from different countries and backgrounds is very positive, as each one contributes from a different perspective.

It was so interesting to meet other female entrepreneurs and entrepreneurs to be, to talk about how we managed to go through the difficulties, the fears, and our successes. We realized, even if we worked in different sectors, that we had a lot in common.

I learned how to spin and dye wool, create biological dyes, create bioplastics, make a leather mold, create fashion from waste, create e textiles, and 3D print molds for soft robotics. I also learned about social media and marketing and met several amazing women innovators running she makes labs all over the world.

Working with tools and methods which are still generally not taught to women, neither at home nor in educational environments, such as electronics and carpentry of bigger scale. It broadened my spectrum to choose what I can work with in art.

I learned the power to be a group of women helping each other to grow in a sustainable way. I really think women need sorority and safe places to develop their project.

Figure 4: Ambassador applicants' experiences during the shemake activities¹⁶

¹⁶ The editable document can be founded in the following link [What did you learn in these activities.docx](#)

Figure 5. Ambassador applicants. Mission-driven¹⁷

¹⁷ The editable document can be founded in the following link [Why do you think you would be a good Ambassador.docx](#)

4.5. Quantitative results

After the application period, **60 applicants** had participated for the twelve Ambassador positions. The majority (**79%**) of applicants were between 25 and 99 years old and represented the learning paths innovators. The two groups of 8-18 year olds (learning paths curiosity) and 18-25 year olds (learning paths discovery) had almost the same number of applications.

Figure 6: The applicants are divided into the 3 age groups.

The majority of attendees of the overall activities are women. There were **3%** of non-binary participants and **4%** of male attendees.

Figure 7: Applicants are differentiated according to their gender.

Almost three quarters of the applicants (**in total 71%**) were from the Leon, Iaac and Waag laboratories. About **10%** of the applicants were from the Onfl lab and another **10%** came from no lab. The fewest applicants came from the Redu and Make Lab.

Figure 8: Overview of the laboratories used by the applicants.

Most participants attended the Biomaterial Barcelona sheMakes activity. In July, **14%** of the participants took part in the Mini-Fabricademy at FabLab Leon. Another **10%** joined the E-Monsters sheMakes activity. Some of the candidates (**8%**) already had extensive experience with textiles and digital fabrication as they had already attended the Fabricademy, while another **8%** had no experience and had not participated in any of the sheMakes activities. The remaining **12%** attended either the REWOOL activity (**6%**) or the Bacteria and Fungi for Textiles activity (**6%**).

Figure 9: Overview of the applicants' activities.

The majority (**62%**) of applicants are from Europe and are from the following countries: Spain, Italy, France, Greece or Switzerland. From these, more than half (**33%**) come from Spain. The minor percentage of **5%** each was either from Italy or France. The remaining **38%** of applicants came from other non-EU countries.

Figure 10: Overview of the countries from which the applicants come.

An interesting fact is that although most of the applications came from Spain, the majority (**48%**) of the applicants have an Italian nationality. Followed by **23%** with Spanish nationality and **12%** with French nationality. While **38%** of the applicants came from other non-EU countries, only **7%** of them did not have European citizenship.

Figure 11: Overview of the nationality of the applicants.

The most popular social media platform used by participants is Instagram (**49%**) and although TikTok is a large and widespread platform, it is not used by any of the applicants. As a professional network and to make social contacts, **30%** of applicants use LinkedIn.

Figure 12: Overview of social media channels used by applicants.

4.6. Results

The following list contains the final selected 12 Ambassadors with their respective Partner lab.

Table 6: List of Ambassadors.

Name	Field	SU activity	Organisation	Origin Country
Petra Garajová	Independent designer	E-monster	IAAC	SK
Tasnim Hussain	Instructor FabLab, Fabricademy alumna	Paros gender vision	IAAC	QAT
Lucía Robles Flórez	Student school	E-monster	LEON	ES
Carla Cabezas del Pozo	Student school	E-monster	LEON	ES
Andrea Wolf-Simone	Teacher of Fashion Design and doing her Masters of the Arts in Design	La collaboration être humain et micro-organismes: pour une industrie textile plus durable	ONLF	CH
Diane Wakim	Computer Scientist, e-textiles researcher	Lab to Lab research and Gender vision	ONLF	FR
Irene Caretti	Fashion designer and digital fabrication, Fabricademy alumna	Innovators Career Mapping	WAAG	NL
Jessica Stanley	PHD smart textiles, Fabricademy alumna	Innovators interview and Career mapping	WAAG	NL

Alexandra Florea	Entrepreneur, scientist	Community engagement	REDU	RO
Marilena Georgantzi	FabLab entrepreneur	Paros gender vision, Lab to Lab research	REDU	GR
Yushing Eng	Entrepreneur	problem solving	MAKE	FR
Camille Le Gal	Entrepreneur	problem solving	MAKE	FR

In the table below, a pairing of transfer labs and Ambassadors is listed as a first draft proposal, to which further changes will be made to ensure its successful implementation.

Table 7: Pairing transfer labs with Ambassadors.

Transfer lab	Country	Ambassador	Partner lab	Task WP2 & 3
Decode Fabrication Laboratory	Greece	Lucia	LEON	Curiosity
VIVA Lab	Portugal	Carla	LEON	Curiosity
VIVISTOP Užupis	Lithuania	Andrea	ONLF	Discovery
Green Fabric	Belgium	Diane	ONLF	Innovation
FarmLab.at	Austria	Irene	WAAG	Innovation
Lottozero textile laboratories	Italy	Jessica	WAAG	Lab to lab projects
RogLab (Rog Centre Creative Hub)	Slovenia	Alexandra	REDU	Community Engagement
Centre for Circular Design, University of the Arts London	UK	Marilena	REDU	Community Engagement
The Icelandic Textile Center, TextileLab	Iceland	Petra	IAAC	Lab to lab project

Textile Prototyping Lab (TPL)	Germany	Tansim	IAAC	Discovery
ZIPHOUSE Design Hub NGO	Moldova	Yushing	MAKE	Business Engagement
Le Textile Lab	France	Camile	MAKE	Business Engagement

Communication of Results

MATRIX communicated all results in the first days of December. As agreed in the Steering Committee, four types of emails were drafted:

- The **winners**: This email included the data consent and the permission for the use of photos and video in the attachments. Regarding the use of videos and images, a specific formulation for the anonymous use of data for minors was proposed, such as using an avatar and naming the winners by their first name.
- A **shortlist** was made for the participants who achieved very good scores, but did not make it to the final selection.
- FLOD formulated two emails, one for the participants who were **not selected** and one for those who had **not participated in any shemakes activity**. In the last case, we suggested to the applicants to find a lab belonging to the shemakes network to get involved in the following actions and events and become Ambassador for the next round.

Finally, all the applicants have been invited to join the newsletter and actively participate in the social networks.

4.7. Next steps

The following steps would be essential to support the Ambassadors in their mission, giving them confidence, motivating them, and encouraging them to further develop the community and bring the shemakes message to the transfer labs.

A sketch of the Ambassadors' process was described in the phase two timeline. It describes the exchange, the support, and the task we required from them.

The next steps are an overview for the Ambassador activities and commitment that WP4 will follow and accompany in close collaboration with the Gurus.

- Ambassadors will exchange their different visions, talk about their backgrounds, motivations for becoming Ambassadors, and experiences in the partner labs telling their purpose, intention, fears, motivations and tell a story (voice and visibility, and values).
- Ambassadors will collaborate with the transfer lab and Guru to develop their own activity, understand all the requirements, and clearly communicate the activity requirements.
- coordination travel with the supervision of Gurus.
- Ambassadors will be in direct contact with the transfer lab contact, Guru. Will be able to support activities in the lab and will be able to offer support to the transfer lab community. Will contribute with visual material to disseminate their activities on the shemakes social media channels.
- Sort and provide documentation material in cooperation with the transfer labs for the following tutorials. With the help of the communication team we will give visibility to their experience in the social media of shemakes (e.g. TikTok).
- There will be a meeting of the activities. In addition, Ambassador exchange between local participants and transfer labs will support the new call for Ambassadors and promote the new generation of shemake leaders.

Adjustments will be made in order to fulfil the successful Ambassadors experience.

5. Visibility

Visibility (Task 4.1) of the reputation strategy is widely promoted through communication actions included in the supporting WP6, primarily using social media as a tool to embed the new values co-created in the shemakes.eu lab contexts as new norms of gendered behaviours and practises. The various activities generated by WP4 (e.g. interviews, videos and network map on the website) from the Advisory Board to the Gurus and Ambassadors are reproduced and promoted through WP6.

This section outlines visibility activities carried out in the first half of the project related to the three tasks in WP4: 4.2 Advisory board, 4.3 Gurus, 4.4 Ambassadors.

5.1. Visibility for Advisors

The Advisory board as a type of inspiration for future female innovators is the most visible aspect of WP4 in the first half of the project. Advisors have been involved in a monthly interview series called “shemakes Voices.”

In M5, a schedule was drafted for the nine interviews, the first of which was held in the third week of September. This task was scheduled in the DoA to start in M6, but we determined that the summer is not a good time to engage the online public with this content, so we shifted it to autumn.

In preparation for this task, during the initial AB call, members of the Advisory board were asked to provide information about themselves (photos, CV, quick Q&A) that allowed the communication team to produce a series of outputs and actions to be taken both before and after each interview. They are summarised in the following table.

Table 8: Communications actions for shemakes Voices.

Channel	Description	Visual
Press release	Wrote and diffused a press release presenting the entire shemakes Voices series and the first three guests. Circulated on PR diffusion websites Europawire , Issuewire, Wire Association, with link back to our website.	
Website news	Posted press release on our website (https://shemakes.eu/blog/shemakesvoices)	18 Sep 2021 in News Shemakes Voices spotlights women innovators in sustainable fashion Designers, policy-makers, thinkers and makers chat in an online video series by shemakes, the EU-funded project to... → Read more

<p>Website events</p>	<p>Upload of each interview in the events section of our website. The next month's interview is always visible. This features the "institutional" graphic with the Advisor's name and promotes the date of the event.</p>	
<p>Facebook & Instagram posts</p>	<p>On social media, we focus on communicating interesting things about the Advisor's career through graphics or animated videos that focus on her as a person and as a professional.</p> <p>The interview is streamed live on Facebook and YouTube.</p>	
<p>Internal channels</p>	<p>The press release and single events are shared to partners and labs through email, and a reminder of the live stream is posted the day of the event on our WhatsApp groups.</p>	
<p>Website blog</p>	<p>After the interview, we transcribe the text to create a long-form blog post with the video embedded. This turns a live content into one that can be easily indexed and read at a later date. The interview link is shared on Facebook and Twitter.</p>	

5.2. Visibility for the Gurus

In this first phase, work has been done to establish internal communication among Gurus. Gurus are constantly in touch with the communications team in order to

provide news about labs' activities and provide materials for project promotion on social media.

For external communication of the Gurus, we've ideated and created the **Network** section of the website, which has a flexible structure that will allow future addition as the project evolves. Gurus are present in this section with their biography, a photo and the link between the Guru and their lab is clearly visible. Our vision is that this profile will be enriched and connections will evolve and be highlighted in coming months.

Gurus have also been contributing to project visibility and content creation. For example, some have written in-depth blog posts providing highlights from some major outcomes or experiences such as the [presence at Fab16's diffused event in August](#), or to share [tips learned from organising an entrepreneurship workshop](#).

Figure 13: Network visualisation on website.

5.3. Visibility for Ambassadors

Discussion and promotion of potential Ambassadors has taken place since the beginning of the project as part of the internal communication. From a public

perspective, the call for Ambassadors was published on the website at the beginning of M11, with a short deadline and a schedule for internal review.

As the call for Ambassadors is not an entirely open call but is limited to those who have been in contact with a Guru and participated in one of the labs activities, the primary method of communication of this call is a direct one between labs and previous participants (using participant registration lists). To support this action, the following activities were undertaken.

1. Created an article/news on the website [LINK] in which potential candidates could read the eligibility criteria, the benefits of being an Ambassador and their involvement in the project. Application documentation is attached at the bottom of the page together with the data consent and an email contact;
2. Disseminated the news on social media through graphics and Instagram Stories with a direct link to the website;
3. Shared the contents with labs and Gurus and asked to spread the call throughout their digital channels (social media, websites, newsletters);
4. Updated all contents when the deadline was extended from Nov. 14 to Nov. 16 and shared with labs and Gurus through email and Whatsapp;

Table 9: Social media promotion of call for Ambassadors.

<p>Instagram and Facebook Posts</p>	<p>First version with the first deadline of Nov. 14.</p>	
<p>Website events</p>	<p>Updated version with the new deadline.</p>	

<p>Instagram</p>	<p>Stories were shared on a daily basis. We have also responded to private messages from users asking info about the application inviting them to get in touch with the team by writing an email to ambassadors@shemakes.eu.</p>	
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<p>Pinned Stories</p>	<p>Eligibility Criteria and What will you have to do as shemakes Ambassador parts of this article were shared and pinned on the profile in order to make the research/informative part easier to potential candidates. A direct link to the call was also added.</p>	
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<p>Twitter</p>	<p>The call was also shared on Twitter on a daily basis, tagging all labs and Gurus in order to be retweeted. We have also retweeted all tweets made by labs, Gurus and interested users.</p>	
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5.4. Next steps

The next steps involve:

- Continuation of shemakes voices.
- Inclusion of Ambassadors' profiles in the network section of the website; the consortium is evaluating if any harm could come to any of the ambassadors due to her involvement in the project and if so, whether her visibility should be reduced. For example, we have asked if Ambassadors who are minors prefer to be represented only with an illustrated profile image or her first name only rather than first and last name and photograph.
- Work with the Ambassadors for content production that will highlight their role.
- Continued involvement of the Gurus in content production in their role as liaison between project actions and public understanding.

6. Conclusion and outlook

Reputation management interim report builds on the strategy presented in the first report and offers during M4 to M12 an accompaniment to the activities of shemakes through Advisors, Gurus and Ambassadors. The three roles generate the call to action in a collective context to build a community of positive change through the advisors' advice, the Gurus' support and content development, and Ambassadors' spirit and experiences carrying the message of the shemakes community. The reputation at the individual level, as promoted by shemakes, thus helps to convey the collective level perception, i.e. the lab, the shemakes network and, more broadly, the reputation of women in the context of innovation in T&C, the project's ultimate goal.

In this document, we present the different perspectives of the Advisors expressed in the key messages and their feedback on the Gurus, and the activities carried out during the first period. The board introduced suggestions to follow for the second period. Beyond the first phase, Advisors with their background and experience shared important points between innovation, industry, STEAM education and policy in the T&C sector to perpetuate shemakes' network with critical pillars for the generation of the future.

WP4 accompanied the Gurus' activities from their conception, realisation, and reflections. The objective of these activities was to understand and support their role in detail commitment and charisma transmitted at each step. Thereby in co-creation with labs and SU partners, we sought to trace a sketch/roadmap for the Ambassadors in their journey to match this process with the transfer labs. Through the activities prepared for the Gurus, we explored the values and how to build a strong network (shemakes weave), contributing in an inspiring and systematic approach.

The first 12 shemakes Ambassadors were selected in the last months, and their first pairing sketch with the transfer labs. Reputation management will continue supporting and developing this process in the next phase.

In addition, WP4 in cooperation with WP1, WP2 and WP3, will follow and work in the outline of possible actions for the next period, with the aim to support the mission of the Gurus and Ambassadors in conjunction with the work of the transfer labs. As this is a project that highly promotes co-creation, it is expected that in particular, Gurus in the company of all SU partners (involved in this process) will guide these actions in conjunction with the other WPs and the task 1.3 network development.

The following steps are further described in each chapter, highlighting the ultimate mission of shemakes to build with the Advisors on Gurus and Ambassadors as tremendous support and contribution with the shemakes community. They will continue the process in creating and sharing a community that inspires the value of the skills and perspectives of greater equity for women, leading to the transition to the second iteration of the shemakes labs activities with the expanded network of 18 labs.

7. Document information

7.1. Revision History

Revision	Date	Author	partner	Description
V 0.1	19.11.21	Adriana Cabrera	MATRIX	First draft and table of contents
V 0.2	16.12.21	Task leaders	MATRIX,TCBL, FLOD	Deliverable before partner review

V 0.3	22.12.21	Nuria Robles, Marion Real, Ista Boszhard, Cecilia Raspanti	LEON, IAAC, WAAG	Proofreading
V 1.0	23.12.21	Adriana Cabrera	MATRIX	Final edits and review for submission

7.2. Statement of Originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation, or both.

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7.4. Disclaimer

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7.5. Acknowledgement

The shemakes.eu project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme for research, technology development, and innovation under Grant Agreement n. 101006203.

8. References

Afuah, A. (2014). *Business Model Innovation*. Taylor & Francis.

Appelo, J. (2019). *Startup, Scaleup, Screwup: 42 Tools to Accelerate Lean and Agile Business Growth*. John Wiley & Sons, Incorporated.

Gloger, B. (2016). *Scrum: Produkte zuverlässig und schnell entwickeln* (5th ed.). Hanser Verlag.

Goll, J. & Hommel, D. (2015). *Mit Scrum zum gewünschten System*. Springer Vieweg.

Poguntke, S. (2019). *Corporate Think Tanks: Zukunftsforen, Innovation Center, Design Sprints, Kreativsessions & Co.* (3th ed.). Springer Gabler.

Vianna, M., Vianna, Y., Adler, I. K., Lucena, B. & Russo, B. (2014). *Design Thinking*. Logos Verlag.

9. Glossary

Listed below are some brief definitions of five different agile innovation methods that Ambassadors can use in workshops and labs activities.

9.1. Agile Innovation methods

Design Thinking is characterised by a cyclical development process and uses rapid prototyping to identify problems, test hypotheses and implement ideas to get quick user feedback (Vianna et al., 2014).

Scrum is an agile framework to facilitate the management of projects and products and is mainly used in the field of software development (Goll & Hommel, 2015). It consists of roles, meetings and tools that establish a team structure with clearly defined workflow steps (Gloger, 2016). Usually, this involves clearly defined cycles of two to maximum four weeks, so-called sprints, for the completion of a work package (Gloger, 2016; Goll & Hommel, 2015).

Design Sprint: The aim of the Design Sprint method is to complete a full cycle of development, including prototyping and testing in just one week (Poguntke, 2019).

Lean Startup is a popular framework for startups and entrepreneurs on how to manage new product development, from the initial idea to finished product, using many Build-Measure-Learn loops (Appelo, 2019).

Business Model Innovation is a framework for value creation with simultaneous changes to the company's value proposition to its customers and the underlying operating model to increase benefits (Afuah, 2014).

10. Annex 1: Gurus' Profiles

Anastasia Pistofidou, IAAC

Anastasia is a Greek architect, researcher, practitioner and educator on digital fabrication, textiles and wearable technologies. She is specialised in hardware development, integration design, rapid prototyping and design to production. Graduated in architecture from AUTH Aristotle University, Thessaloniki, and holds a Master's Degree from IAAC (Institute for Advanced Architecture of Catalonia) where she is still a lecturer.

In addition, she is co-founder of fabtextiles.org, a research laboratory on textiles, soft architectures and innovative materials, as well as co-founder of Fabricademy Textile and Technology Academy.

Nuria Robles, LEON

Nuria is a Mechanical Engineer and Master in Quality, Environment and Occupational Risk Prevention. She worked as an engineer for more than 13 years until she fell in love with the world of FabLabs. As the manager at Fab Lab León, where she has been employed since 2012, she is an instructor for the FabAcademy and Fabricademy programs and mentor for the Educational Programs for children, youth and adults. These programs introduce Digital Fabrication and the Maker philosophy into the daily lives of young people, and are focused on finding solutions to everyday problems and training them through the creation of their future portfolio.

In this context, Nuria launched PODEROSAS in 2015, a program where girls from 6 years old combine technology with manual tasks to create original projects.

Cristina Olivotto, ONLF

As a physicist by training, Cristina started to work in the field of science communication and formal and informal science education during her PhD at the University of Milan, Italy. She has extensive experience in working with international contexts and with European organisations, including the European Space Agency where she worked in the educational team for five years.

In Leiden, the Netherlands she worked for Sterrenlab – the company that she founded – to organise science camps and activities for children and teenagers. In 2016 she co-founded the first FabLab in Geneva, Switzerland Onl’Fait, where she is currently employed as FabLab manager. She is involved in all the Onl’fait activities related to youngsters, schools and professional reintegration.

Cecilia Raspanti , WAAG

Cecilia Raspanti is a creative researcher in fashion & textiles and a digital fabrication expert. She is the co-founder of the educational world wide distributed programme, Fabricademy: textile and technology academy, and co-founder/LabLead of the prize winning TextileLab Amsterdam at Waag. Here she leads the creative research and technological development of new concepts and alternatives visions for the textile and clothing industry.

Graduated from Polimoda Fashion Institute of Florence, in Fashion and knitwear design. Experienced in fashion, knitwear/textiles, she enjoys bridging that traditional craftsmanship knowledge with a variety of technologies, as opportunities to explore alternative production processes. Always inspired by nature’s magic, her latest works involve biotechnology and chemistry principles to rediscover colour and material properties for a more sustainable path.

Beatriz Sandini, WAAG

Beatriz Sandini is a designer and concept developer at Waag's TextileLab Amsterdam, where she collaborates on reframing the future of textiles and fashion by working on several research and educational projects across the globe.

Being born in Brazil, Beatriz studied business administration, worked as a product manager for a big fashion retailer for many years, and later founded her own fashion brand. Since 2018 she has lived in Amsterdam, where she kicked off her journey into a

creative multi-disciplinary design path by researching innovative biomaterials and digital fabrication techniques.

In April 2020, she graduated from the Fabricademy course at Waag with her own research project Ephemeral Fashion Lab and Cor Botanicals, where she continues to explore more sustainable and responsible alternatives to the fashion industry.

Andreea Sofronea, REDU

Andreea is an artist by education, a green social entrepreneur by vocation, and both project manager and designer by profession. While being aware of the added value of diversity related to her professional and academic background and current occupation, she doesn't underestimate the challenges it brings.

One can easily make a parallel between the winding path of her personal and professional backgrounds. Both can be reflected by her current soul project – REDU (Iași, Romania) a social enterprise that uses garment waste from local clothing/textiles factories to create new 'green' products. Since 2017, she has been a co-owner of this green social enterprise, together with colleagues/former employees and also the mother organisation Mai Bine (For the better), where she started as a volunteer about 12 years ago.

At REDU she started as a facilitator for creative recycling, after that as a sewer, then as a designer, afterwards as project manager, and trainer on the topic of ecology and human ecology workshops.

Victor Senave, MAKE

After studying business administration and performing arts throughout the world – Lille, San Francisco, Ho Chi Minh City and Paris, Victor wrote a thesis on the link between arts and social impact, which led him to start his professional career at makesense.

His first missions consisted of tours around France to raise awareness amongst thousands of people about commitment – whether through social entrepreneurship, civic engagement, redefining one's work or building positive communities. Several topics are at the core of these tours: youth, social innovation, tech for good or even biomimicry.

After taking hundreds of trains, Victor became responsible for makesense's awareness programmes, thinking of new ways to reach more people, while

maximising conversion rates of sensitised people towards concrete action for a more sustainable and inclusive society.

11. Annex 2: Gurus, transfer labs and Ambassadors

This table is a first sketch of the roadmap for the Gurus, the transfer labs and the Ambassadors to guide actions connected to the respective tasks WP1 WP2 and WP3. Plenary meetings will support these points to disseminate information collectively to support the development of team activities.

It is not intended to exempt either Gurus' or Ambassadors' efforts and will be readjusted for their successful adaptation.

	INPUT	GURUS	TRANSFER LABS	AMBASSADORS	MONTH
Introduction of shemakes: 1 Background - Evaluation (session for all)	<i>SU members and especially Gurus will introduce the project, the objectives shemakes vision</i>	Receiving Gurus will give their vision of the activities and experiences through the first phase. Giving: the Gurus will ask about the	The laboratories' own methods and backgrounds will be explored to enrich the shemakes practises, as well as the interests of the paths and ideas to be	Ambassadors will exchange their different visions, talk about their backgrounds, their motivations for becoming Ambassadors and their experiences in the partner	M13

		<i>and modus operandi.</i>	conditions and the requirements and expectations through the M13 - 18.	developed.	labs.	
		Technology sciences. Maker movement.				
2	Exploration: local ecosystem and motivation in the shemakes activities (split section)	<i>Map of the Activities, key partners and role models, how the Partner labs develop their activities.</i>	Gurus will help the transfer labs to understand their local ecosystems, as was done during the first phase. In case of Curiosity task the guru can provide, provide tools and special training for the girls to exercise their public	Explore their local ecosystem identifying key partners (Actors 4ple helix, research, academia, institution) to develop the activities, observing and promoting participation as a shemakes lab for the recruitment of interested attendees.	Give the Ambassadors confidence and how to project themselves into the shemakes network.	M14
		Input from the Gurus' contributions and motivations.			<i>Purpose</i> Intention fears, motivations, Advice	

			speaking skills.		Tell a story (voice, visibility, and values)	
Preparation: of <i>the activity</i> 3 session for all <i>and co-creation</i> <i>divided per task</i>	Tools, methods, skills, mapping elaborated by the transfer labs (especial input by mini-workshops)	The Gurus will support the knowledge transfer actions for the task they are leading.	They will adapt the activity using the shemakes tools and methods with their suggestions, constraints or needs concerning the development of the activity.	Ambassador will in parallel collaborate with the transfer lab and Guru for the development of his own activity, understanding all the requirements and making a clear communication of the activity requirements.	M14	
	Activity canvas					
	Review preparation					
		Communication activities in the network (event, channels, formats, showcase).	Coordination travel with Gurus			

<p>Making "the activity" (<i>split activity divided per task and schedule</i>)</p>	<p>Open Toolkit guidelines for activities.</p>	<p>Gurus will be in close contact with their transfer labs and Ambassadors to support all coordination of the individual process during this period.</p>	<p>Preparing the lab, materials checklist and coordination of the Ambassador's activity.</p>	<p>Ambassadors will be in direct contact with the transfer lab contact, Guru. Will be able to support activities in the lab and will be able to offer support to the transfer lab community. Will contribute visual material for the dissemination of their activities on the shemakes social media channels.</p>	<p>M15 – M16</p>
		<p>Review lessons learn, reflections and Improvements. In this session Gurus Ambassadors and labs will exchange experiences and support needed for the next activities, and this open discussion will provide a space for sharing personal challenges, skills and competences.</p>			
<p>5 Transfer (<i>split section</i>)</p>	<p>Documentation and deliverable, e.g documentation open Toolkit.</p>	<p>Gurus will communicate and support the documentation process in the Open Toolkit as well as in the formal</p>	<p>Will document their journey by: 1. documenting their activity Open Toolkit 2. providing the necessary information for the preparation of the</p>	<p>Sort and make available documentation material in cooperation with the transfer labs for the next tutorials with the help of the communication team</p>	<p>M17</p>

			part delivered for the project.	deliverable.	we will give visibility to their experience in the social media of shemakes (e.g. TikTok).	
6	Next steps <i>preparation call</i> <i>new action</i> <i>(session for all)</i>	Guidelines promotion Ambassadors and local shemakes lab ecosystem engagement	Encourage the Ambassadors and transfer labs to involve the new shemakes leaders in the further exchange and active community engagement.	They will show their results and collaborate with the Gurus and communicate to give visibility to their process, finally they will be supported in the process of a new call for Ambassadors and the steps to follow in the months of M18 to 24, inviting them to participate in events such as the shemakes conference.	There will be a meeting of the activities. Ambassador exchange between local participants and transfer labs will help and promote the new call for Ambassadors, promoting the new generation of shemake leaders.	M18

12. Annex 3: Scoring Ambassadors

Scoring Rubric		Activity and contact to a guru/ Community	Shemakes activities learnings	Mission Driven	Labs experience	teaching experience	General questions
		Have you been participate in a shemakes activity? Have you had a chance to work with or meet a shemakes "guru" listed below? (Gurus are our representatives and workshop leaders) Online presence	What did you learn in these activities, and why do you think it was important to your growth as a person?	Why do you think you would be a good shemakes Ambassador? What you can offer to others, but also what you can gain or how this opportunity will help you in any way.	Have you participated in any relevant laboratories or workshops, or do you have any specific training that might be relevant to your role as an Ambassador?	Do you have any experience teaching anything or explaining things to a group?	What is your English proficiency level? Or other languages?
1	Low Score Beginning/Emerging	no contact until now	have a notion of what was done in the activity	no exact idea	no touch points until now	no exact idea	No foreign language skills
5	Medium Score Developed	have contact from time to time	found this activity meaningful	think that you can do that	own participation in event / teaching a small group /	think that you can do that	speaking english
10	High Score Exemplary	in permanent exchange with gurus or labs	Found the activity very meaningful, identify with the values and continue to explore opportunities for shemakes.	they want to share knowledge with others, to help and support activities, want and have taught people or learn for training or she/he already has participated in such experience and would be an excelent participant	she/he is very involve in activites in the lab, participate and trained own groups (several times)	already has other similar Experiences in teaching or training, helping others	speaking english and other languages

Annex 4: Presentation introduction Reputation Management

